

EM-TECH

D5.3 – Functional evaluation of integrated control strategy

EM-TECH – Innovative e-motor technologies covering e-axles and e-corners vehicle architectures for high-efficient and sustainable e-mobility

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
AFM	Axial Flux Motor
CAN	Controller Area Network
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
MiL	Model-in-the-Loop
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation

UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
XiL	X-in-the-Loop

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1 Publishable Executive Summary

1.1 Overview of project

This report is dedicated to the implementation of project tasks aimed at developing and validating a new generation of electric drives for automotive transport. The project considered two key technological lines: the use of In-Wheel Motors (IWM) in an e-corner configuration, and the use of axial electric machines as part of an e-axle system. The main objective of this stage was to preliminarily test the performance of individual components and subsystems, as well as to validate control algorithms in conditions close to real-life operation.

The utilization of IWMs and axial motors creates opportunities for improvements in energy-efficiency, improved dynamic characteristics, and the implementation of new vehicle motion control functions, including the distribution of traction and braking forces at the level of individual wheels. These technologies create the basis for more flexible powertrain architectures and expand the potential of integrated control systems.

The report presents the results of experimental studies conducted on assembled test benches to evaluate the correct functioning of control elements and analyse the effectiveness of the interaction between hardware and software components of the e-corner and e-axle systems.

1.2 Deliverable Objective and Results

In the framework of this step, a transition was made from research in the Model-in-the-Loop (MiL) environment, carried out in Task 5.2, to experiments in the Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) environment. Control algorithms were previously developed and configured in the MiL environment, after which they were validated and tested in real time on dSPACE platforms. This made it possible to evaluate the performance and quality of the controllers before their subsequent integration with the e-corner and e-axle systems, planned as part of Work Package 6 (WP6).

2 Introduction

This task realises a logical transfer from the MiL studies in Task 5.2, required for the controller tuning, to the HiL experiments, where the controllers will be tested on real-time dSPACE platforms before the e-corner and e-axle integration in WP6. On this stage, the corresponding HiL environments will be assembled by TUIL (e-corner) and USR (e-axle). The test programme will include especially two Use Cases (UCs) as follows.

- UC1 (e-corner): Test target: e-gear control; Evaluation: control performance, with focus on the novel functionalities (e.g., ABS modulation as well as longitudinal and pitch control) enabled by the superior dynamics of the EM-TECH IWMs.
- UC2.1 (e-axle) and UC2.2 (e-corner): Test targets: brake blending and functional safety; Evaluation: The brake blending control and fail-safety control under consideration of two actuators (electric motor and

brake-by-wire system for e-axle) and three actuators (electric motor, e-gear, and brake-by-wire system for e-corner).

3 Description of test setups for HIL experiments

3.1 E-corner test setup

A real-world simulation test rig was implemented to validate the developed electric vehicle powertrain, which features the ability to change the winding configuration (e-gearing technology) and switch between them while driving. This rig is designed for conducting HIL experiments and provides conditions that are as close as possible to real-world operation.

The stand includes a dynamometer unit that simulates mechanical load in accordance with a virtual vehicle model integrated into the XiL environment. The inverter is controlled via a controller area network (CAN) interface, which allows control signals to be transmitted and real-time data to be received. Additionally, a separate interface is provided for controlling the e-gear system, allowing the configuration of windings to be changed and the operating modes of the electric machine to be switched directly during experiments. A photo of the developed test rig and an overview is provided with Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 Close-up photo of the control electronics

The development of such an experimental platform is a key step in the comprehensive evaluation of the system. It allows not only to verify the correct functioning of control algorithms and equipment in various operating scenarios, but also to analyse the performance and energy-efficiency of the power plant with different winding configurations and in different operating modes. This, in turn, makes it possible to objectively compare the potential characteristics for different types of vehicles, optimise the switching strategy and justify the choice of electric drive architecture for specific applications.

3.1.1 Hardware components

The test bench is designed for experimental validation and research of the characteristics of the developed electric motor with an integrated e-gearing system. The configuration of the test bench is based on the principle of simulating the propulsion as applied to a quarter of a car: it includes power electronics that control the electric motor and the electric motor itself, which reproduces the operation of one wheel of a vehicle. The test bench is illustrated in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2 E-corner test setup at TUIL

The test bench is based on the AVL DynoSpirit test bench, adapted for testing electric machines. The bench system provides high accuracy in setting the shaft rotation speed, which allows simulating the movement of a car wheel in various modes. At the same time, the torque on the electric motor shaft is measured, which makes it possible to analyse the characteristics of the IWM. A direct oil cooling system is used to cool the electric motor (see Figure 3-1). The test rig includes an oil station that circulates and cools the oil in the motor circuit. The oil station and power electronics (inverter) are connected to the test bench cooling system, which uses a mixture of water and glycol. This design allows a stable thermal regime to be maintained during long and high-load tests.

The test bench allows to:

- accurately reproduce the shaft speed equivalent to the speed of a vehicle wheel,
- measure torque and other motor operating parameters with high accuracy,
- conduct tests in various operating modes, including transient and dynamic modes,
- investigate the efficiency and performance of the e-gearing technology.

The EM-TECH IWM is equipped with a winding configuration mechanical switch, which improves energy-efficiency and expands the operating range in terms of torque and speed. The e-gear system is integrated into the IWM design and controlled via a dedicated interface, enabling real-time configuration switching during testing.

The e-gear control strategy requires the coordinated operation of the power electronics, controlled by the electric motor and the contactor that switches the winding configuration. To test and evaluate the system, an inverter for the electric motor must be created that can work with such a device. To simplify concept validation, the e-gear has its controller, and the synchronisation of the inverter and the mechanical part of the contactor is performed on a rapid prototyping device. Therefore, the test setup includes a test bench controller that controls the dynamometer, an inverter that controls the motor, and an e-gear controller as shown in Figure 3-3. The mechanical part of the e-gear is connected to the phase wires of the IWM.

Figure 3-3 Component diagram of the test bench

Figure 3-3 shows a block diagram of the electric motor control system integrated into the test bench. The system is based on a multi-level architecture and provides both power drive control and real-time switching of e-gear winding configurations. Top level control: The top level uses the dSPACE rapid prototyping systems, which interacts with the virtual vehicle model via an ethernet connection in a XiL environment. This system generates control commands for the lower-level controllers, including torque, speed, and winding configuration tasks. Middle level test bench controllers: Control signals from dSPACE are transmitted via CAN bus to two controllers: (i) AVL test rig controller controls the inverter, generating torque or speed commands, and processes telemetry, and (ii) e-gear controller controls the motor winding configuration switching system. The latter receives commands from dSPACE via the CAN interface and generates 24 V PWM signals for the e-gear actuators. Lower-level power section: The inverter is powered

by a 750 V DC source and generates three-phase signals for the electric motor via phase cables. It is controlled via the CAN interface from the test bench controller and transmits feedback signals about the system status (speed, currents, voltages, temperature, etc.) in real time.

The e-gear system is powered by 24 V DC and controlled via pulse width modulation (PWM). It is directly connected to the electric motor and provides winding connection changes to extend the operating speed range and improve energy-efficiency.

The e-gear switch contacts directly switch the motor's phase wires, which complicates controller design, as the motor inverter is not always directly connected to the motor.

Opening or switching phase wires while the motor is running is potentially dangerous for several reasons:

- Probability of sparks and electrical discharges when wires are disconnected in a high-current circuit (especially at 750 V DC), electric arcs can form, causing damage to contacts, heating, and danger to equipment and personnel.
- Disruption of the motor control algorithm the inverter controller calculates phase currents and voltages in real time to maintain the set torque and speed. A sudden change in phase connections leads to incorrect sensor readings and disruption of vector control, which can cause jerks, overheating, or motor failure.
- Impact on protection systems current and voltage surges during winding switching can trigger the inverter's protection algorithms, leading to emergency shutdowns or false alarms.
- Dynamic loads on mechanical parts sudden changes in electrical connections can cause sharp changes in torque on the motor shaft, which creates increased loads on gearboxes and bearings.

The following section will describe in detail the developed controller, which allows safe control of e-gear winding switching, minimising the risks of sparking, control algorithm violations, and emergency motor stops.

3.1.2 Software architecture

The block diagram in Figure 3-4 shows the interaction model of the electric motor control system components for an automotive transmission test bench in the XiL simulation environment. The architecture provides integration of various communication buses (CAN, user datagram protocol (UDP), simulation buses), as well as implementation of basic functions for calculating and controlling gear shifting.

Figure 3-4 Simulink model of the software implemented on the test rig

TestBenchStatus subsystem:

The TestBenchStatus block generates and transmits data on the status of the test bench. It includes:

- SIM_BUS — a simulation bus for data exchange with other systems,
- UDP_BUS — an interface for data exchange with external XIL network nodes via UDP, and
- The block's output data, which is connected to other subsystems, ensuring synchronization of information about the current status of the test complex.

CAN_2 subsystem:

The CAN_2 block processes data exchange via the CAN bus and communicates with Puma, which controls the dynamometer, including:

- SimBUS, Gear_shifting, CalcBus inputs,
- Formation of PUMA_CAN, Motor status, ZerotorqueState messages, which are transmitted to the Gear transition subsystem and other blocks, and
- Provides communication with the model of real control units (e.g., PUMA ECU) and electric motor controllers, forming correct CAN messages.

CAN_1 subsystem:

The CAN_1 block provides communication with the E-gear control unit via the CAN bus:

- Receives Motor status and Gear_shifting signals, and
- Generates E-gearCAN messages used in the Gear transition and Calculation subsystems.

Calculation subsystem:

The Calculation block performs computational functions related to the logic of the drive and transmission operation:

- Receives data from the SimBus bus, as well as inputs from Dummy and Puma_CAN,
- Forms the calcBUS bus, which is transmitted to CAN_2,
- Implements data processing and conversion algorithms, ensuring the coordinated functioning of models and control units, and
- Calculates motor parameters and performs protective functions, such as limiting torque surges or excessively high requests.

DummyModel subsystem:

The DummyModel block is used to emulate missing physical system modules:

- Receives signals from the SimBus and generates the DummyBus output, which is transmitted to the Calculation block.

The main purpose of the block is to replace the real electric motor with a mathematical model during preliminary testing or debugging of individual control system components. When using a model instead of a real motor, a simplified dynamic diagram allows you to analyse the system response, evaluate gear shifting characteristics, and perform calculated estimates of dynamics and electrical efficiency without the need to connect physical equipment. This makes it possible to conduct testing at early stages of development, reducing risks and time costs when integrating real components.

XiL Communication Subsystem:

The XiL Communication block provides a communication interface between the simulation environment and external components:

- Provides data exchange between the SIM_BUS, UDP_BUS, and controller, and
- Used to integrate the model into the XiL test circuit, ensuring interaction between simulation modules and test bench hardware components.

The model implements a closed architecture in which data about the test bench status is transmitted via simulation and CAN buses to calculation blocks and gear shift algorithms. The CAN_1 and CAN_2 subsystems ensure data coordination between different control modules.

The Calculation and DummyModel blocks implement the computational and emulation parts of the system, while Gear transition controls the gear shift modes depending on the state of the electric motor and torque.

Gear transition subsystem:

The Gear transition block is responsible for implementing the logic of transition between transmission modes:

- Receives input signals Motor status and ZerotorqueState,
- Uses the E-gearCAN bus to coordinate with the CAN_1 block, and
- Generates the Gear_shifting output, which controls the gear shifting process. This ensures realistic simulation of the transmission operation depending on the state of the electric motor.

To ensure correct and safe gear shifting in the e-gear system, the following sequence of actions, shown in the Figure 3-5, must be performed.

Figure 3-5 Gear transition logic

- In the first stage, the system determines the presence of a gear shift request by comparing the current and required gears.
- After detecting the request, the electric motor torque is set to zero, and its nulling is confirmed. This ensures that no torque is transmitted to the drive during the shift.
- Next, the inverter's PWM modulation is disabled, which prevents unwanted currents from occurring during the mechanical change of gear position.
- After that, the inverter is switched to the appropriate mode, and a command to shift gears is issued.
- After successful mechanical shifting, the system confirms the gear change, reactivates PWM modulation, and restores control of the electric motor.
- In the final stage, a request for the required torque is sent.

Compliance with this sequence ensures smooth and reliable e-gear shifting without shock loads, slippage, or loss of power system stability. This architecture allows testing and verification of electric motor and

transmission control algorithms in the XiL environment without using a real car, ensuring high reproducibility, safety, and efficiency of testing.

3.2 E-axle test setup

The distributed XiL test environment at USR has been developed to provide a realistic and flexible platform for advancing electric powertrain testing, with a specific focus on the EM-TECH project for evaluating the TRX on-board axial flux motor (AFM) and implementing advanced vehicle controllers. Its primary objective is to bridge the gap between purely simulated models and physical motor prototypes, enabling accurate assessment of dynamic behavior, efficiency, and energy consumption across experiment facilities at different universities and research centers. By integrating real hardware with real-time simulation, the distributed XiL test environment offers a powerful means to validate system performance prior to full vehicle integration, thereby accelerating development while reducing cost and risk.

3.2.1 Hardware components

The smart e-axle test configuration at USR integrates essential hardware to establish a real-time platform for advanced powertrain testing. The TRX AXF300-85s on-board AFM, shown in Figure 3-6 (a), is installed and coupled to the dynamometers via a bellows-type flexible coupling, enabling precise measurement of key performance parameters such as torque, speed, and efficiency. To drive the AFM, the I&M inverter, shown in Figure 3-6 (b), is employed to supply three-phase AC power for accurate torque control. In addition, the inverter supports CAN communication, allowing the exchange of critical control and monitoring signals for seamless integration within the XiL environment.

Figure 3-6 (a) TRX on-board AFM and (b) I&M high-performance Inverter

The advanced powertrain setup is supported by a dedicated high-voltage power supply, which ensures stable and adjustable DC voltage for the inverter rated from 0 V to 800 V. To maintain operational safety and performance of the inverter and AFM, a sophisticated thermal management system has been implemented for both, as shown in Figure 3-6. The AFM is oil-cooled and lubricated, reducing electrical and magnetic losses while minimizing bearing friction, whereas the inverter is liquid-cooled to handle the thermal stresses of sustained high-power operation of the MOSFET. The cooling infrastructure includes pumps, radiators, fans, valves, flow meters, and pressure/temperature sensors, all integrated with the control platform to provide real-time monitoring and adaptive cooling control. Additionally, accelerometers and torque/speed sensors are mounted on the motor and dynamometers to capture vibration, load, and performance data during operation.

Figure 3-7 Thermal cooling system for (a) Inverter and (b) AFM

This hardware is embedded within the broader XiL framework, with all subsystems connected through the dSPACE MicroAutoBox II controller for real-time operation and data acquisition. The architecture enables seamless interaction between hardware components and simulation models, ensuring the AFM and inverter operate within safe boundaries while accurately reproducing real-world vehicle conditions. Collectively, these hardware components form a robust, modular, and flexible e-axle testbed, capable of supporting advanced validation of powertrain dynamics, control strategies, and thermal management of the AFM and inverter. Further details on the test bench configuration can be found in deliverable D6.1.

3.2.2 Software architecture

The software architecture of the distributed XiL setup follows a structured scheme that combines physical hardware testing with virtual vehicle simulation through secure XiL communication, shown in Figure 3-8. At USR, the AFM test bench serves as the primary hardware element, controlled in real time by a dSPACE MicroAutoBox II, which implements the overall controller logic. The controller processes reference wheel speed and motor torque signals received from TUIL and generates corresponding AFM torque outputs, which are measured from the Dynamometer. These torque values are passed through a local virtual gearbox model to compute effective wheel torque. Through the encrypted virtual private network (VPN)-based XiL network, this effective torque is transmitted to TUIL, where a dSPACE Scalexio platform executes the full vehicle model, including wheel dynamics. The vehicle model evaluates system response and produces wheel speeds, which are sent back to USR as feedback signals. Thus, the exchanged messages consist mainly of effective wheel torque (USR to TUIL) and reference wheel speeds (TUIL to USR), with data sources being the AFM measurements at USR and the vehicle simulation results at TUIL. This closed-loop communication ensures synchronization of physical and virtual subsystems and provides the basis for evaluating distributed electric powertrain architectures under realistic conditions.

Figure 3-8 Block diagram of the real-time distributed XiL testing framework

4 Functional evaluation of the components

4.1 E-corner test setup

Preliminary functional tests were conducted on a dynamometer as part of the IWM testing. The purpose of this stage was to perform a basic check of the operability of key components of the power and control systems under controlled laboratory conditions. During the tests, not only was the operation of the electric motor in various modes evaluated, but also the functionality of the e-gear system, which is responsible for switching winding configurations to optimise drive performance. The results obtained confirmed the correctness of the basic control algorithms and established key operating parameters that will be used to refine the test plan for further research.

During the first stage, a series of verification tests were conducted to verify the dynamometer's ability to reproduce the required operating modes. These tests confirmed the ability of the test bench to maintain the specified rotation speed and torque values with the required accuracy, as well as to ensure a smooth and controlled change in the electric motor speed within the possible range. These tests confirmed the correct operation of the measurement and control complex, and set the basic parameters for subsequent functional tests of the drive system.

Figure 4-1 shows the dynamics of tracking a specified rotation speed profile using a dynamometer. The red line shows the required speed, and the blue line shows the actual measured rotation speed. The tests were conducted in the form of a stepwise change in the required speed with fixed time intervals at each level. The results demonstrate that the test bench control system provides stable tracking of the specified profile with high accuracy across the entire speed range. The observed short-term deviations during transitions between steps correspond to the inertial processes of acceleration and deceleration and are within acceptable limits, which confirms the correct functioning of the speed control loop.

Figure 4-1 Dyno velocity tracking profile

4.1.1 E-gear controller and architecture of the control loop

The next stage of testing checked the operability and stability of the electric motor winding configuration switching system, namely the e-gear. The main foci have been on the correct execution of switching commands, the stability of the power unit in transient modes, and the evaluation of the time required to complete the switching. The presented Figure 4-2 shows characteristic diagrams of the system's operation when the e-gear status changes. At the moment the command is given, there is a brief decrease in torque and a readjustment of the PWM modulation mode, after which the system stabilises at a new level. The measured switching time was approximately 260 ms, which significantly exceeds the expected values. This switching time significantly limits the applicability of this system in dynamic modes requiring a quick response and indicates the need to refine both the hardware and algorithmic parts of the e-gear.

Time evaluation of the e-gear switching stages:

- Switching time: ≈ 260 ms
- Torque decrease: 20 ms
- PWM off: 1 ms
- **Gear switch: 215 ms** (very inconsistent, ranging from 200 to 350 ms)
- PWM on: 1 ms
- Torque setup: 40 ms

Figure 4-2 Transition state of the e-gear

For a detailed analysis of the stability of the winding switching system, an extended series of tests was conducted in various modes, covering a wide range of electric motor speeds and torques. The purpose of these tests was to determine the reproducibility and stability of the switching time depending on operating conditions. During the tests, it was found that the current version of the system demonstrates satisfactory performance only at speeds up to 400 rpm and torque not exceeding 400 Nm. When these parameters are exceeded, significant fluctuations in switching time and a decrease in operational stability have been observed.

To quantitatively evaluate the results, a probabilistic approximation of the shift time distribution was performed separately for the upshift and downshift modes. The approximated distributions are shown in Figure 4-3 below and allow for a clear comparison of the nature and spread of switching times in different modes of the e-gear system, as well as determining the average values and dispersion of delays.

To evaluate the characteristics of the e-gear system, experimental studies were conducted to determine the switching time of the electric motor windings. The tests were carried out in various motor operating modes and as the measurement results in Figure 4-3 show, the most probable switching time is approximately 350 ms. This corresponds to the mean expected value for this specific system setup.

The measurement method involved is recording the control commands sent from the e-gear controller and recording the moment of the actual change in winding connections using position and current sensors. For each mode, a series of several tens of switching cycles was performed, which made it possible to obtain statistically significant data and estimate the average, dispersion, and maximum switching time.

It was noted that switching to a lower gear occurs slightly faster, which is due to the peculiarities of the mechanical design of the e-gear system: when switching to a lower gear, moving the anchors inside the

mechanism requires less effort and time. Nevertheless, the overall dispersion of shift times and maximum values remain quite high, which limits the accuracy and stability of the system in real-world conditions.

The main reason for these deviations is the limited performance of the control electronics, which do not provide the necessary speed of processing control signals and adequate coordination with the mechanical part. As a result, the controller is unable to respond instantly to shift commands, which increases the response time spread and slows down the entire operation.

Figure 4-3 Comparison of the e-gear downshifts and upshifts durations

These results highlight the need to optimise the hardware platform and software control algorithms to reduce shift times and improve the repeatability of operations. A more advanced version of the controller should be developed in the future, which will allow the e-gear system to be used in conjunction with other engine control algorithms and expand the functionality of the test bench. The current version of the controller is significantly limited in both performance and functionality, which imposes significant restrictions on the efficiency and accuracy of the system.

4.2 E-axle test setup

To validate the operational reliability and functionality of the distributed HiL environment, as well as to enable further evaluation of the proposed controllers reported in deliverable D5.2, several vehicle manoeuvres were carried out using the e-axle test within the distributed ethernet XiL environment and the on-board AFM with a virtual transmission. The AVL virtual transmission was implemented and deployed on the rapid prototyping device (dSPACE MicroAutoBox II) at USR. It is important to note that, due to mechanical constraints associated with the coupler currently connecting the dynamometer to the spline shaft of the AFM on the USR test rig, the testing setup is limited in terms of the achievable speed

range and torque transfer capability. Consequently, constant vehicle speeds of 10, 20, and 30 km/h, with the AVL virtual transmission configured for two different gears, were selected for the test campaign to ensure stable and safe operation during data collection.

4.2.1 Constant Speed Test at 10 km/h – Gear 1 vs Gear 2

For the e-axis testing procedures, once the state machine status at USR has been verified to match the state machine signal sent from TUIL and the communication delay is confirmed to be within an acceptable range, USR activates the signal request and transmits the measured signal to TUIL. TUIL then controls the vehicle manoeuvres using their vehicle model.

Figure 4-4 Vehicle speed tracking performance at 10 km/h using (a) Gear 1 and (b) Gear 2

Figure 4-4 illustrates the vehicle speed tracking response at constant speed of 10 km/h with Gear 1 and Gear 2 configurations. In both cases, the actual vehicle speed (blue solid line) closely follows the desired speed reference of 10 km/h (red solid line). The system reaches steady-state operation after approximately 22 seconds for both Gear 1 and Gear 2. During the steady-state phase, the vehicle speed remains generally stable, although slight deviations between the actual and desired speeds are evident—more pronounced in the Gear 1 case. The transient deviations observed during the acceleration phase are likely influenced by torque and speed limitations on USR test bench side, imposed by the coupler constraints discussed earlier. Overall, the results confirm that the control system achieves reliable tracking performance under both gear configurations at the specified operating speed.

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Figure 4-5 Motor speed tracking performance at 10 km/h using (a) Gear 1 and (b) Gear 2

Figure 4-5 compares the motor speed request from TUIL with the actual motor speed measured by the speed sensors at USR at constant speed of 10 km/h with Gear 1 and Gear 2 configurations. It is important to note that USR receives the vehicle's wheel speed from the vehicle model via ethernet communication from TUIL. However, the plots shown here represent the equivalent motor speeds derived by applying the appropriate gear ratios for Gear 1 and Gear 2. This allows for a direct comparison between the commanded and actual motor speeds within each gear configuration. In Gear 1, Figure 4-5 (a), the motor reaches and maintains a speed slightly above 500 RPM. In Gear 2, Figure 4-5 (b), due to the gear ratio difference, the required motor speed is lower, stabilising around 420 RPM. In both cases, the AFM speed closely follows the TUIL speed request signal, with a minor ripple observed at steady-state which is attributed to minor drivetrain oscillations. These results confirm the correct operation of the virtual gearbox logic and motor speed control loop, ensuring speed synchronisation across the XiL environment.

4.2.2 Constant Speed Test at 20 km/h – Gear 1 vs Gear 2

Test scenarios of constant vehicle speed manoeuvres at 20 km/h, using Gear 1 and Gear 2 configurations, were performed independently. The results below illustrate and compare the vehicle and motor speed responses under these two gear settings.

Figure 4-6 Vehicle speed tracking performance at 20 km/h using (a) gear 1 and (b) gear 2

As shown in Figure 4-6, both gear configurations demonstrate satisfactory tracking of the actual vehicle speed (blue) with respects to the target speed of 20 km/h (red). The system reaches steady-state operation at different times: approximately 20 seconds for Gear 1 and around 30 seconds for Gear 2. Due to the torque request limitations of the AFM, the amplified torque after the AVL gearbox model is greater in Gear 1 than in Gear 2, since Gear 1 provides a higher gear ratio. Although the torque request reaches the maximum threshold in both cases, Gear 1 is able to deliver a higher effective torque to the wheels, thereby reducing the rise time required to reach steady-state speed compared to Gear 2. Despite the difference in stabilization times, the final speed tracking performance is satisfactory for both configurations.

Figure 4-7 Motor speed tracking performance at 20 km/h using (a) Gear 1 and (b) Gear 2

Figure 4-7 illustrates the AFM motor speed at 20 km/h together with the corresponding motor speed command issued by TUIL. It can be observed that the AFM motor speed closely follows the TUIL speed request in both cases, with a slight ripple at steady-state attributed to minor drivetrain oscillations. As for the final steady-state motor speed, it is expected that the values for Gear 1 and Gear 2 are approximately double those observed during the 10 km/h constant-speed manoeuvres, since the motor speed is linearly proportional to the vehicle speed.

4.2.3 Constant Speed Test at 30 km/h – Gear 2

Due to the speed and torque limitations of the coupler, the constant-speed manoeuvres were carried out up to 30 km/h only in Gear 2. Operating at a constant speed of 30 km/h in 1st gear would cause the motor speed to exceed the current coupler’s speed limit. Therefore, the vehicle speed tracking and motor speed tracking results at 30 km/h in Gear 2 are presented in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8 (a) Vehicle speed tracking performance at 30 km/h with Gear 2 and (b) Motor speed tracking performance at 30 km/h with Gear 2

Figure 4-8 demonstrates satisfactory vehicle speed and motor speed tracking performance between 40 s and 140 s. The rise time for the vehicle to reach the target speed is approximately 38 seconds, which is longer than the rise time observed in the 20 km/h manoeuvre with Gear 2. The increased rise time is due to the higher vehicle speed combined with the limited output motor torque. It should be noted that the current coupler used in the USR test bench imposes certain limitations on the speed tracking performance. However, once the new coupler is installed, the rise time for vehicle speed tracking is expected to be significantly reduced, enabling a proper evaluation of the test campaign targeted in deliverable D6.2 without performance degradation.

5 Energy-efficiency evaluation

5.1 E-corner

Preliminary experiments made it possible to evaluate the energy consumption of the electric motor in various operating modes and with different configurations of the e-gear system windings. Figure 5-1 shows the dependence of power consumption on shaft speed for several selected winding configurations. The measurements allow comparing the efficiency of the motor at low and medium velocities, as well as identifying the effect of winding switching on energy consumption. The results show that the optimal choice of winding configuration reduces energy losses and increases the overall efficiency of the system. The effect is noticeable, and could provide a benefit for the overall vehicle energy-efficiency.

Figure 5-1 IWM energy consumption for the different gears; Blue line (Gear 1); Red line (Gear 2)

5.2 E-axle

Based on the collected voltage and current signal from the power supply, the total energy consumption caused by the inverter and motor can be measured and calculated. Alternatively, the mechanical power produced from the motor at different vehicle manoeuvres can be determined using the collected torque and speed data from the dynamometers.

5.2.1 Constant Speed Tests – Gear 1 vs Gear 2

Data collected from the vehicle manoeuvres enabled the evaluation of motor energy consumption and energy-per-distance for both gear configurations, as summarised in Table 5-1. The calculations are based on vehicle acceleration from standstill to the target speed over a defined duration, with the overall time period ranging from 5 s to 140 s.

Table 5-1 – Energy consumption and efficiency comparison between Gear 1 and Gear 2 at various constant speeds

Gear	Speed (km/h)	Total electrical energy drawn (Wh)	Energy-per-distance (Wh/km)
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1	10	53.78	147.18
2	10	55.01	150.88
1	20	64.39	89.36
2	20	65.53	92.68
2	30	83.32	79.71

At the lowest speed of 10 km/h, energy consumption is marginally lower when operating in Gear 1, with 53.78 Wh compared to 55.01 Wh in Gear 2. Both gears show relatively high energy-per-distance values, reflecting the inefficiency associated with very low-speed operation. At 20 km/h, absolute energy demand increases in both configurations, with Gear 1 consuming 64.39 Wh and Gear 2 65.53 Wh, respectively. When comparing to energy-per-distance, Gear 1 achieves 89.36 Wh/km compared to 92.68 Wh/km for Gear 2, indicating a modest efficiency benefit for Gear 1. This corresponds to an improvement of approximately 2.4 %, which is attributed to the torque–speed operating point of the motor in each gear. At 30 km/h, results are available only for Gear 2, due to speed limitations of the coupler in Gear 1. Gear 2 records the highest absolute consumption of 83.32 Wh; however, the energy-per-distance decreases to 79.71 Wh/km, highlighting improved efficiency at higher speeds as relative losses are reduced.

In conclusion, the analysis indicates that Gear 1 provides slightly better efficiency than Gear 2 at 10 km/h and 20 km/h, though the improvements are marginal. Gear 1 is therefore advantageous for low-speed operation, while Gear 2 demonstrates superior efficiency at higher steady-state speeds. These findings reinforce the importance of selecting the appropriate gear ratio depending on the driving condition and provide valuable input for the development of a rule-based gear-shifting strategy. The results also establish a baseline for subsequent testing and performance characterisation of the e-axis system across a wider range of operating conditions in Task 6.2, leading to deliverable D6.2.

6 Conclusion

This report presents the results of preliminary validation of the developed components and systems intended for use in electric vehicle propulsion systems. It was demonstrated that the hardware and software solutions developed operate correctly at the level of integration into the vehicle architecture. The functional tests carried out demonstrated the operability of key control elements and confirmed their ability to work together as part of a complex system.

The assembled test benches and XiL environment made it possible not only to control individual components, but also to test their behaviour at the system level in conditions close to real-life operation. This made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the interaction between new types of drives, controllers and control algorithms, as well as to confirm their compliance with the design objectives.

The experiments also made it possible to identify the system's weaknesses, which should be eliminated in subsequent stages of development. In particular, the current version of the e-gear controller has limited performance and functionality, which significantly reduces the overall potential of the system and limits

the applicability of the developed solutions in more complex control algorithms. Eliminating these limitations will allow the system to be used in a significantly larger number of algorithms, including advanced strategies for coordinated drive and brake control.

In addition, the test infrastructure created made it possible not only to check the functionality of the components, but also to evaluate the energy-efficiency of the entire system, including measuring the energy consumption of the car model, taking into account real losses in components and the dynamic characteristics of actuators. This made it possible to analyse the impact of the actual operation of the drive and control systems on the behaviour of the vehicle and its power consumption.

6.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

At this stage, no deviations from the project's objectives and tasks have been identified. The work performed is fully in line with the target plan, and the results obtained confirm the correct functioning of the developed systems in the XiL environment. The tests conducted demonstrated the functionality of components and confirmed the control and interaction between subsystems.

Minor deviations were observed in the testing methods employed, which is due to the technical limitations of the prototypes and test benches. In particular, instead of testing the braking force mixing algorithms, as originally planned, experiments were conducted to evaluate the energy-efficiency of the electric motor in various operating modes. This change was due to the fact that the current prototype has limitations on the maximum permissible rotation speed, and the existing test bench designed for HiL testing does not allow tests related to extreme braking modes to be carried out.

Despite these changes, the tests presented clearly demonstrate the functional capabilities of the system components and confirm the positive effect of using new types of drives in terms of energy-efficiency. Thus, the work performed does not have a negative impact on the progress of the project and is in line with its overall objectives.